

BA'ZI BIR NILPOTENT ZINBIEL ALGEBRALARIDA ROTA – BAXTER OPERATORLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada noassotsiativ algebra bo'lgan 4 o'lchamli nilpotent Zinbiel algebralarida vazni λ bo'lgan Rota-Baxter operatorlari o'rganilgan. Bundan tashqari ba'zi 4 o'lchamli nilpotent Zinbiel algebralarida vazni nol bo'lgan Rota-Baxter operatorlari matritsalarini qurilgan. Bunda 4 o'lchamli nilpotent Zinbiel algebralarining 2010-yilda chop etilgan "Zinbiel algebralarining ayrim sinflari tasnifi" nomli maqoladagi tasnifidan foydalanilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: noassotsiativ algebra, vazn, operator, maydon, akslantirish.

ROTA-BAXTER OPERATORS IN SOME NILPOTENT ZINBIEL ALGEBRAS

ABSTRACT

In this article studied Rota-Baxter operators of weight λ in 4-dimensional nilpotent non-associative Zinbiel algebras. In addition, for some 4-dimensional nilpotent Zinbiel algebras, matrices of Rota-Baxter operators with zero weight are constructed. Here we used the classification of 4-dimensional nilpotent Zinbiel algebras from the article "Classification of some classes of Zinbiel algebras" published in 2010.

Keywords: non-associative algebra, weight, operator, field, mapping.

Rota – Baxter algebrasi ehtimollar nazariyasidagi ba'zi bir masalalarni yechishdan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, matematika va fizikaning ko'plab sohalarida o'z tadbig'iga ega, jumladan sonlar nazariyasi, kvazisimmetrik funksiyalar, Li algebralari va Yang – Baxter tenglamalari. Rota – Baxter operatorlari Baxter tomonidan ehtimollar nazariyasidagi [3] analitik formulani yechish uchun kiritilgan. Bu operatorlar, matematika va matematik fizikaning boshqa sohalariga ham aloqador [4]. [1] ishda 3-

o‘lchamli nilpotent assotsiativ algebralar uchun Rota-Bakster, Reynold va Nijenhuis operatorlari tasnif qilingan.

F maydon ustida A assotsiativ algebraning Rota – Baxter operatori deb quyidagi tenglikni qanoatlantiruvchi $P: A \rightarrow A$ chiziqli akslantirishga aytiladi:

$$P(x)P(y) = P(xP(y) + P(x)y + \lambda xy), \quad \forall x, y \in A, \lambda \in F$$

Takidlab o‘tish kerakki, agar $P - \lambda \neq 0$ vaznga ega Rota – Baxter operatori bo‘lsa, u holda $\lambda^{-1} P -$ vazni 1 ga teng Rota – Baxter operatori.

Ushbu ishda biz ba’zi bir 4 – o‘lchamli nilpotent Zinbiel algebralarida Rota – Baxter operatorlarini tasnifladik.

$$P \text{ operatorning matritsasi } - \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{14} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{24} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{34} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} \end{pmatrix}$$

$\lambda=0$ bo‘lgan xol

$$P(x)P(y) = P(xP(y) + P(x)y)$$

Quyida ba’zi bir 4 – o‘lchamli nilpotent Zinbiel algebralar [2] ishda keltirilgan:

$$\alpha_1: \quad e_1 \circ e_1 = e_3, \quad e_1 \circ e_2 = e_4, \quad e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, \quad e_3 \circ e_1 = 2e_4.$$

$$\alpha_2: \quad e_1 \circ e_1 = e_3, \quad e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, \quad e_2 \circ e_2 = e_4, \quad e_3 \circ e_1 = 2e_4.$$

$$\alpha_3: \quad e_1 \circ e_1 = e_2, e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_2 \circ e_1 = 2e_3, e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_2 = 3e_4,$$

$$e_3 \circ e_1 = 3e_4;$$

$$\alpha_4: \quad e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_1 = -e_3, e_2 \circ e_2 = e_4.$$

Teorema 1. 4 – o‘lchamli α_1 nilpotent Zinbiel algebrasida Rota – Baxter operatori matritsalarini quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

Algebra	Rota Baxter operatorlari $\lambda=0$ bo‘lgan xol	Cheklovlar
α_1	$P_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{11} = a_{44}$
	$P_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{3}a_{21} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}; a_{11} = 0$

	$P_3 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{31} & 0 & \frac{1}{2}a_{11} & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{31} & \frac{1}{3}a_{11} \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}; a_{11} \neq 0;$ $a_{43} = a_{31}$
	$P_4 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 3(a_{43} - a_{31}) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{31} & 0 & \frac{1}{2}a_{11} & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & \frac{1}{3}a_{11} \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}; a_{11} \neq 0;$ $a_{43} \neq a_{31}.$

Teorema 2. 4 – o‘lchamli α_2 nilpotent Zinbiel algebrasida Rota – Baxter operatori matritsalarini quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

Algebra	Rota Baxter operatorlari $\lambda=0$ bo‘lgan xol	Cheklovlar
α_2	$P_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{22} = a_{44}$
	$P_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{22} \neq a_{44}; a_{11} = 0;$ $a_{22} = 0.$
	$P_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & \frac{1}{2}a_{22} \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{22} \neq a_{44}; a_{11} = 0;$ $a_{22} \neq 0.$
	$P_4 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{31} & 0 & \frac{1}{2}a_{11} & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{31} & \frac{1}{3}a_{11} \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{22} \neq a_{44}; a_{11} \neq 0;$ $a_{22} = 0.$
	$P_5 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{2}{3}a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ a_{31} & \frac{1}{4}a_{11} & \frac{1}{2}a_{11} & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{31} & \frac{1}{3}a_{11} \end{pmatrix}$	$a_{22} \neq a_{44}; a_{11} \neq 0;$ $a_{22} \neq 0.$

Teorema 3. 4 – o‘lchamli α_3 nilpotent Zinbiel algebrasida Rota – Baxter operatori matritsalarini quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

Algebra	Rota Baxter operatorlari $\lambda=0$ bo‘lgan xol	Cheklovlar
α_3	$P_1: a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{22} = a_{23} = a_{24} = 0,$ $a_{34} = a_{44} = 0$ $a_{31}, a_{32}, a_{33}, a_{41}, a_{42}, a_{43}$ – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} = 0;$ $a_{21} = 0;$ $a_{44} = 0.$
	$P_2: a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{22} = a_{23} = a_{24} = 0;$ $a_{31} = a_{32} = a_{33} = a_{34} = 0$ $a_{41}, a_{42}, a_{43}, a_{44}$ – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} = 0;$ $a_{21} = 0;$ $a_{44} \neq 0.$
	$P_3: a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{22} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{33} = 0,$ $a_{34} = a_{44} = 0,$ $a_{43} = a_{21},$ $a_{21}, a_{31}, a_{32}, a_{41}, a_{42}$ – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} = 0;$ $a_{21} \neq 0.$
	$P_4: a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{23} = a_{24} = 0,$ $a_{31} = a_{32} = a_{33} = a_{34} = a_{43} = 0;$ $a_{44} = \frac{1}{2}a_{22};$ a_{22}, a_{41}, a_{42} – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} \neq 0;$ $a_{33} = 0;$ $a_{21} = 0.$
	$P_5: a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{33} = a_{34} = 0;$ $a_{31} =$ $-\frac{3a_{21}^2}{a_{22}},$ $a_{32} = -3a_{21},$ $a_{43} = 3a_{21},$ $a_{44} = \frac{1}{2}a_{22};$ $a_{21}, a_{22}, a_{41}, a_{42}$ – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} \neq 0;$ $a_{33} = 0;$ $a_{21} \neq 0.$
	$P_6: a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{31} = a_{32} = 0,$ $a_{34} = a_{42} = a_{43} = 0;$ $a_{11} = 3a_{33},$ $a_{44} = \frac{1}{2}a_{22};$ a_{22}, a_{33}, a_{41} – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} \neq 0;$ $a_{33} \neq 0;$ $a_{21} = 0;$ $a_{31} = 0.$
	$P_7: a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{32} = a_{34} = a_{43} = 0;$ $a_{11} = 3a_{33},$ $a_{42} = \frac{3}{2}a_{31},$ $a_{44} = \frac{1}{2}a_{22};$ $a_{22}, a_{31}, a_{33}, a_{41}$ – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} \neq 0;$ $a_{33} \neq 0;$ $a_{21} = 0;$ $a_{31} \neq 0.$
	$P_8: a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{31} = a_{34} = a_{42} = 0;$ $a_{11} = 3a_{33},$ $a_{32} = a_{43} = a_{21},$ $a_{44} = \frac{1}{2}a_{22};$ $a_{21}, a_{22}, a_{33}, a_{41}$ – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} \neq 0;$ $a_{33} \neq 0;$ $a_{21} \neq 0;$ $a_{31} = 0.$
	$P_9: a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{34} = 0;$ $a_{11} = 3a_{33},$ $a_{32} = a_{43} = a_{21},$ $a_{42} = \frac{3}{2}a_{31},$ $a_{44} = \frac{1}{2}a_{22};$ $a_{21}, a_{22}, a_{31}, a_{33}, a_{41}$ – lar, cheklovlarga bog‘liq holda ixtiyoriy.	$a_{22} \neq 0;$ $a_{33} \neq 0;$ $a_{21} \neq 0;$ $a_{31} \neq 0.$

Teorema 4. 4 – o‘lchamli α_4 nilpotent Zinbiel algebrasida Rota – Baxter operatori matritsalarini quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

Algebra	Rota Baxter operatorlari $\lambda=0$ bo'lgan xol	Cheklovlar
α_4	P_1 : $a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{22} = a_{23} = a_{24} = 0$, $a_{34} = a_{44} = 0$ $a_{31}, a_{32}, a_{33}, a_{41}, a_{42}, a_{43}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} = a_{44}$; $a_{12} = 0$.
	P_2 : $a_{11} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{22} = a_{23} = a_{24} = 0$, $a_{31} = a_{32} = a_{33} = a_{34} = a_{44} = 0$ $a_{12}, a_{41}, a_{42}, a_{43}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} = a_{44}$; $a_{12} \neq 0$; $a_{22} = 0$.
	P_3 : $a_{11} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{31} = a_{33} = a_{34} = 0$, $a_{43} = a_{44} = 0$; $a_{32} = -\frac{a_{22}^2}{a_{12}}$; $a_{12}, a_{22}, a_{41}, a_{42}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} = a_{44}$; $a_{12} \neq 0$; $a_{22} \neq 0$.
	P_4 : $a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{22} = a_{23} = a_{24} = 0$, $a_{31} = a_{32} = a_{33} = a_{34} = 0$; $a_{41}, a_{42}, a_{43}, a_{44}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} =$ 0 ; $a_{22} = 0$; $a_{11} =$ 0 .
	P_5 : $a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{22} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{31} = a_{32} = 0$, $a_{33} = a_{34} = a_{43} = a_{44} = 0$; $a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{41}, a_{42}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} =$ 0 ; $a_{22} = 0$; $a_{11} \neq$ 0 .
	P_6 : $a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{31} = a_{32} = 0$, $a_{33} = a_{34} = a_{43} = 0$; $a_{44} = \frac{1}{2}a_{22}$; a_{22}, a_{41}, a_{42} - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} =$ 0 ; $a_{22} \neq 0$; $a_{33} =$ 0 .
	P_7 : $a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{21} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{31} = a_{32} = 0$, $a_{34} = a_{43} = 0$; $a_{22} = \frac{1}{2}a_{11}$, $a_{33} = \frac{1}{3}a_{11}$, $a_{44} = \frac{1}{4}a_{11}$; a_{11}, a_{41}, a_{42} - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} =$ 0 ; $a_{22} \neq 0$; $a_{33} \neq$ 0 .
	P_8 : $a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{22} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{32} = a_{33} = 0$, $a_{34} = a_{43} = a_{44} = 0$; $a_{31} = \frac{a_{21}^2}{a_{11}}$; $a_{11}, a_{21}, a_{41}, a_{42}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} \neq$ 0 ; $a_{33} = a_{44}$; $a_{12} = 0$.
	P_9 : $a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{33} = a_{34} = a_{43} = a_{44} = 0$; $a_{22} = \frac{a_{12}a_{21}}{a_{11}}$, $a_{31} = -\frac{a_{21}^2}{a_{11}}$, $a_{32} = -\frac{a_{12}a_{21}^2}{a_{11}^2}$; $a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{21}, a_{41}, a_{42}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} \neq$ 0 ; $a_{33} = a_{44}$; $a_{12} \neq 0$; $a_{43} = 0$.
	P_{10} : $a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{33} = a_{34} = a_{44} = 0$; $a_{21} = -\frac{a_{11}^2}{a_{12}}$, $a_{22} = -a_{11}$, $a_{31} = -\frac{3a_{11}^3}{a_{12}^2}$, $a_{32} = -\frac{a_{11}^2}{a_{12}}$; $a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{41}, a_{42}, a_{43}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} \neq$ 0 ; $a_{33} = a_{44}$; $a_{12} \neq 0$; $a_{43} \neq 0$.
	P_{11} : $a_{11} = a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{33} = a_{34} = 0$; $a_{31} = -\frac{2a_{21}^2}{a_{22}}$, $a_{32} = -2a_{21}$, $a_{43} = -\frac{1}{2}a_{21}$, $a_{44} = \frac{1}{2}a_{22}$; $a_{21}, a_{22}, a_{41}, a_{42}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} \neq$ 0 ; $a_{33} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{33} = 0$.
	P_{12} : $a_{12} = a_{13} = a_{14} = a_{23} = a_{24} = a_{34} = 0$; $a_{22} = \frac{1}{2}a_{11}$, $a_{31} = \frac{4a_{21}^2}{3a_{11}}$, $a_{32} = -2a_{21}$, $a_{43} = -\frac{1}{6}a_{21}$, $a_{44} = \frac{1}{4}a_{11}$; $a_{21}, a_{22}, a_{41}, a_{42}$ - lar, cheklovlarga bog'liq holda ihtiyoriy.	$a_{11} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{21} \neq$ 0 ; $a_{33} \neq a_{44}$; $a_{33} \neq 0$.

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